

AN ANALYSIS OF COMMUNITY ASSETS ON LIVELIHOODS OF FARMING
COMMUNITY IN TEHSIL FAISALABAD

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Abstract

The state of farmers' livelihoods is significantly impacted by community resources. Due to less capital and least developed community assets income level in rural areas is low as compared to urban areas. Synthesis of available literature has shown a positive impact of community assets on infrastructure development and income level, especially in rural areas. This study was explored the community assets on livelihoods of farming community in Tehsil Faisalabad. The study's main goal is to analyze the influences on livelihood assets using composite indices or in conjunction with other factors that affect livelihood outcomes. Researchers have expected to have established an inverse link between rural poverty and community assets. Based on this assertion, the study was assessing the sustainable livelihood assets of farming households in Tehsil Faisalabad, Pakistan. There are total 346 union councils in Tehsil Faisalabad, from 346 union councils of rural and urban, rural union councils was selected purposively. Out of total rural union councils, two union councils were selected purposively, three villages were selected from each union councils and 20 farm households were selected from each village thus making a sample size of 120 farm household heads. For the purpose of gathering information on pre-defined objectives, a valid and trustworthy interview schedule was created. The analysis of data revealed that most of the respondents have farming as source of income. Mostly (70%) of the respondents belonged to low-income families. Most of the respondents were illiterate. Data also shows that most of the farmers were small farmers (less than 12.5 acers). The data regarding differ community assets suggest that respondents in the study area possess very less community assets that's why they are unable to develop their life style. The results also describe a close relationship between community assets, income level and livelihood opportunities for respondents in the study area. The research's conclusions suggested that forming alliances with nearby companies, governmental bodies, and community organizations can aid in ensuring that communal assets are adequately maintained and administered. Considering the present finding it was suggested that Govt. should facilitate community member.

Community assets such as schools, hospitals and govt. buildings should develop in rural areas to motivate farmers and community members. Participation of rural communities in decision making process should maximize. Local resources should use to develop financial and physical resources of community. Training and infrastructural material should provide in rural areas to develop the assets and to maximize per capita income in rural areas.

INTRODUCTION

Financial capital is a key component of sustainable capital. The financial resources mentioned here include cash, liquid assets, pensions, and remittances. Some of these capitals are evident, like land, money, buildings, and machines, while others are less obvious, including social networks, knowledge, and good health. They are significant; however, it is obvious that the distribution of their use varies over time and from household to household. It will be simpler to evaluate each capital's contribution and investigate the vulnerability context in which it exists at the home once the balance has been determined using the capital pentagon. Each of the previously covered capital assets includes an index or indication that displays its availability, accessibility, and other crucial details that might be utilized to reach specific households. It is also important to keep in mind that a single household asset, like land, might produce a number of advantages. For instance, if a family has safe access to land, they are more likely to have substantial financial assets since they can use the land for both loan collateral and productive reasons. According to literature, household capitals varied in their levels of resilience when it came to the severity of shock or stress. For instance, while some assets, like currency and social networks, can be volatile and depend on the influx and egress of household members, others, like cash, can alter very little over time. Drought will also affect natural capital, reducing yield, but may not have much of an impact on other assets. A severe drought could, of course, have a long-term negative influence on some types of capital, such as social and human capital, while having little effect on others (Bebbington *et al.*, 2011).

The evaluation tool was created to examine the effects of various natural resource and management strategies on a certain target population. The management of local natural resources is the main area of local community and individual interest. The word "PRA"

is used to describe the expanding family of strategies and techniques that allow locals to contribute their expertise and perspective to decision-making. The five phases that make up the 5 livelihood assets—human, social, physical, natural, and financial are the foundation of the sustainable livelihood strategy (Wellard *et al.*, 2014).

Since they may easily be converted into any form of money, financial assets are the most diverse types of assets. It includes saving, credit and loans for agriculture, as well as remittances from abroad and within the country. Many households in poverty lack sufficient financial resources. The quantity and quality of these assets that the household owns heavily influence the livelihood strategies and income-generating activities at the household level (Ellis, 2015).

Just providing locals with compensation will not result in the conservation of tropical forests. They rely on forest resources to supply the global community with environmental benefits from their forests or to make up for a restriction on their use. The social component of conservation measures' implementation in the past received far too little consideration. The use of economic instruments to achieve natural resource conservation often results in quick fixes. Financial remuneration is viewed as a welcome addition to regular income, but it does not always alter how natural resources are used. Instead, the development of sustainable forest management practices that equally consider ecological, economic, and social sustainability should be the goal. Analyzing alternate sources of income is vital to preserve value of natural resources forests by minimizing the impact of households that rely on forest products for their daily needs (Lax and Krug, 2013).

Rural residents engage in a variety of economic activities to support their needs for a living, based on their access to and ownership of productive capital.

Everything required for sustaining life is included in livelihood, which is larger than revenue. It is made up of these planned activities that men and women engage in to create their livelihoods and provide the means for a household to survive. Using five capital assets, households participate in a variety of livelihood-generating activities. Natural, physical, social, financial, and human capitals are among them. The choice of livelihood possibilities and the wellbeing of the household are significantly influenced by access to various degrees and combinations of assets. The sustainability of livelihoods is an emerging concern, particularly in developing nations where there is a high prevalence of poverty, hunger, and malnutrition as well as economic sluggishness and subpar agricultural practices. He further argued that a way of life is continual when it can withstand shocks and stresses, maintain or increase its assets and income. It is also continual when it generates net benefits for other ways of life both locally and globally, as well as over the short and long term. A livelihood includes people, their capacities, and means of subsistence such as income and assets, as well as sufficient stocks and flows of food and money to meet fundamental demands of life. (Fanget *et al.*, 2014).

Notwithstanding the fact that rural people are primarily to blame for the degradation of the resources, the idea of evaluating the livelihood strategies of these communities has real-world application in resource conservation. The capital configurations of persons who were able to leave poverty and the capitals' applicability to other environments for subsistence are of interest to study. Also, it would be interesting to assess the ability of one capital to be replaced by another, supposing, for instance, that a sure cluster of social or human capital may make up for a deficiency in financial capital (Rakodi, 2014).

Physical capitalism is crucial to the growth of the rural economy. Infrastructure such as access to markets, roads, transit, medical facilities, educational institutions, technical colleges, and universities were all part of this capitalism. Many people have varied opinions on how important physical assets are. Others place more weight on transportation, educational institutions, and communication infrastructures. A high value on the availability of roads, electricity, and

water. Roads reduce travel times and give low-income residents access to markets. Electricity also plays a significant part in the development of rural areas since it helps select the sites of industrial companies that might give the impoverished of rural people's access to jobs and money. The provision of safe drinking water can also help prevent illness and disease in rural regions (Israr and Khan, 2014).

The assets may be both tangible and intangible. Physical resources are considered tangible assets, whereas claims and access are considered intangible. When a livelihood source has a sustained positive net benefit on other sources of livelihood and contributes to the stability of environmental assets, it is considered to be environmentally sustainable. In the daily lives of rural households, each of these capitals is as significant. It is essential for rural households' survival and well-being. Rural residents struggle to earn the necessary income and build assets because they have limited or no access to these resources. A sort of asset in which capital is embedded in people is called a human asset. Human capital emphasizes the value of labor, health, education, job capacity, and skills as resources for securing a living. Of these, labor is the most valuable asset, but it is insufficient for ensuring household livelihoods; when improved through education, training, and other skills, it becomes a very powerful tool for ensuring the livelihood of poor households. The labor efficiency is improved by knowledge, excellent health, skills, and motivation. Nonetheless, there are significant disparities in access to these resources between the wealthy and the poor, rural and urban populations, and both men and women. There are variations in literacy levels and educational access between men and women. More precisely, social capital stresses ties to family, kinship, and close friends who support the household in times of need. You may think of your connection as an investment in your two futures. Our partnership is built on mutual respect and trust (Udoh *et al.*, 2017).

The aims of this study to analyzed the potential analysis of community assets on livelihood of farming community in Tehsil Faisalabad. The rural small farmers lacked assets to support their families. The small farmers' unique asset status is uncovered tiny farmers' living conditions. Researchers have established an inverse link between rural poverty and

asset-based households that can sustain themselves. The study will assess the sustainable livelihood assets of farming households in Tehsil Faisalabad, Pakistan. The number and type of assets they own and the level of household poverty and what can be done to enhance their livelihoods with the help of agricultural extensions. Agricultural extensions bring about a change in the lives of the rural and improve their livelihood assets, residents and development through awareness.

Objectives

- To investigate the demographic characteristics of the respondents
- To identify the perceptions of respondents regarding community development assets
- To investigate the impact of community assets on livelihood of farming community
- To probate hindering factors that are affect involve in developing the community assets
- To suggest a way in the community development assets

Review of Literature

Ellis (2019) showed that the specific capital status of the small farmers revealed the level of life of small farmers with limited resources for a living. The output of the livelihood may increase through the efficient utilization of family land. The key factors that could boost livelihood output were the size of the household work force and the level of education of household labor earners. The number of dependent family members may prevent agricultural households from growing the amount of income they generate. Also, via efficient use, physical and financial capital can boost the productivity of a livelihood. The life of rural farmers is also improved by access to service providers of social assets, who promptly offer to farmers either on loan or in cash. Due to the low level of trust, only a small number of people belong to institutions, which ultimately has no impact on the livelihood of rural farmers. According to the study's findings, the following policy recommendations are made: continual use of natural resources in terms of effective land use through the use of agriculturally intelligent practices and technologies. The agricultural departments and other related stakeholders must alter their strategy and vision for agricultural growth in

order to inform rural farmers, particularly young ones, about the most cutting-edge agricultural innovations that can be used depending on socioeconomic circumstances bringing it even more in line with market trends and the effects of climate change. In the framework of the sustainable livelihood paradigm, the traditional home structure needs to be examined in terms of female dependency and empowerment. Therefore, the study region has enormous potential for livestock rearing, and the farmers should be encouraged to run the livestock business profitably. To build social capital, these organizations must be formed in the region. The local government system required to be examined in the context of the sustainable livelihood paradigm in order to create beneficial policies, such as formal financial support, to improve the lives of rural residents.

Cook (2005) Human capital is defined as knowledge, skills, labor capacity, and good health that are dependent on the amount and caliber of workers available. Access to education and health care, as well as investments in these fields, are crucial for boosting both agricultural and non-agricultural activity in rural areas, which in turn affect household livelihood opportunities and returns on other capital. The resource flows and services derived from natural resource stocks make up natural capital. It is crucial for those whose livelihood depends primarily or partially on activities involving natural resources. The infrastructure is the tangible capital required to support assets and is regarded as a crucial asset since they have an impact on how readily available and accessible commodities and services are. The financial capitals are the readily available stocks, including financial resources, savings, and consistent inflows of cash. Of the five capitals, money serves a variety of functions, and having access to it enables individuals to have secure and fruitful lives. It consists of networks, formally organized groups, reciprocal ties, and exchanges. This money made it easier for people to work together and cut down on transaction costs, which may serve as the foundation for unofficial safety nets for the poor in rural areas. The results of livelihood strategies are the livelihood outcomes. Depending on the situation, it might be categorized as more food security, increased income, less vulnerability, improved wellbeing, and more sustainable use of natural resources.

Goatley (2007) stated that rural regions are ecosystems made up of several diverse sources, and that villagers use a variety of resources and assets to shape their method of subsistence. Most of the time, unchecked industrial exploitation is more detrimental than improper or unconscious use of resources. Because of the excessive strain on resources, rural poverty is currently regarded as one of the unsustainable elements in resource consumption. As a result, aiding the poor villages should include changing their way of life as well as providing financial support. In this sense, rural capital and assets can serve as the fundamental building blocks for accomplishing the objectives of sustainable rural livelihood. Thus, it had been attempted to look into and address the assets and possessions of the villagers in this study. In addition to attempting to quantify the standard of living in Taybad Flat and Karat Dehestans' rural communities, the following questions are also attempted to be addressed: Are the claims and resources of rural people consistent throughout the case study area or not? Which assertion contributes the most to rural life? And ultimately, which village is in a better position than the others?

Shen (2008) stated that according to past studies, the economic aspects of rural areas were the main focus of research on sustainable community livelihood development. Several academics have adopted and supported the idea of continual livelihood, which has transformed the investigating trend and turned to a more thorough perspective to explore agricultural and rural concerns. Also, the study of tourism shifts from a narrow perspective that only considers the effects on the economy, trade, and environment to a more expansive perspective that fully evaluates the influence of tourism on communities. Recent years have seen several academics make the observation that, in the context of sustainable livelihood, an examination of community livelihoods that includes both income and assets supporting a livelihood is more thorough than one that focuses solely on assets or income. However, only a small number of studies on tourism have considered livelihood assets as a factor determining income. Using the sustainable livelihood approach, it was discovered, for instance, that the absence of capital for a livelihood is a significant factor in the people's low tourism revenue.

Devkota (2010) reported that the fact that rural people are primarily to blame for the depletion of these resources, it has been noted that the idea of evaluating the livelihood strategies of these groups is useful in resource conservation. It is crucial to examine the capital constellations of people who were able to overcome poverty and determine whether these constellations may be applied to various contexts for generating income. Also, it would be interesting to assess the ability of one capital to be replaced by another, supposing, for instance, that a certain constellation of social or human capital may make up for a deficiency in financial capital.

Zhang (2018) reported that it has been hypothesized that the livelihood resources have a substantial impact on the possibilities for livelihood and the income of tourism communities. Spatial disparities are frequently present depending on the type of natural tourism community and its level of development.

Ukanwa (2018) suggested that diverse livelihoods capital help differentiate the livelihoods of rural households. According to reports, livelihood assets are the foundation of community livelihoods and a requirement for sustainable community livelihood development. Also, the growth of specific assets that support livelihoods diversifies communal livelihoods.

They think that a more socially cohesive community can diversify livelihoods. Without "social capital," Mitra even asserted, "access to any form of livelihood is nearly inconceivable." The main sources of livelihood in traditional rural communities are natural resources and human resources. As a result, agriculture is the indigenous communities' main source of livelihood. The more the natural and human resources, albeit they may occasionally work as temporary migrant workers elsewhere, the more probable it is that the farmers will choose agriculture as their livelihood. Increases in farmers' financial, social, and physical assets encourage them to choose non-agricultural livelihoods as society develops. This leads to diversified livelihoods or livelihood transformation; the higher the accumulated assets for livelihood, the more likely it is that the farmers will select a livelihood with a higher income. Farmers' decisions on the agricultural livelihood activities to engage in are also influenced by the kind and accumulation of their assets. The local farmers' decision to choose worm gathering as a livelihood was

significantly impacted negatively by education, household size, and distance to a worm collecting station. Social assets have an impact on community livelihoods, policies, and processes, which helps with the efficient spatial distribution of other resources. Lack of tourism knowledge and expertise, a lack of awareness of tourism development, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of power are significant barriers to community inhabitants' participation in tourism. As a result, the assets that support a livelihood have a significant impact on the livelihood choices of community members.

Abbassi *et al.*, (2020) reported that it has been demonstrated that the majority of Nigerian rural farmers are impoverished, indicating that their asset bases are insufficient to maintain them. Given the significant relationship between wealth and poverty, it is imperative to evaluate the rural farmers' asset profiles. The availability of the household's collection of assets has an impact on the alternatives for its way of life. They allow households to react to shocks including poverty, climatic change, price adjustments, flood, and drought among others. Due to factors including poverty, inflation, risky price changes, and climate change, some households are unable to live sustainably. A household's ability to survive depends on the assets it owns and the extent to which it can use those assets to deal with change and support a sustainable way of life a family with a higher level of education and a greater likelihood of implementing sustainable livelihood options that improve food security. The use of multi-dimensional approaches has gained importance in the research of living standards and human wellbeing, which has moved away from the use of uni-dimensional approaches. One of the first theories to transfer the emphasis from one-dimensional metrics to multidimensional measures was the Sen's capability approach. This method gauges people's wellness using the ideas of "functioning" and "capabilities." In response to Sen's capability theory, the Human Development Index was created (HDI).

The Millennium Development Goals programmed was introduced by the UNDP (MDGs). Together with monetary aspects of wellbeing, this effort also called for non-monetary interventions.

Hassan *et al.*, (2021) reported that there are resources that are endowed in the homes as assets and provide for living. It requires time and financial resources to acquire or create. The Department for International Development (DFID) has recognized five kinds of assets as the foundations of livelihood: human, natural, financial, physical, and social. These capitals could be used in combination to some extent. Since individuals are people first and foremost, the livelihood approach is seen as requiring capital selection for successful livelihood outcomes. A single type of capital is insufficient to produce the whole range of desired as well as various essential livelihood outcomes.

Soni (2022) suggested that among many other ideas to gauge people's well-being, livelihood studies have attained much focus in the past few decades to comprehend the factors that affect socioeconomic status, particularly for rural residents in developing nations. Well-known international organizations look at the rural population's socioeconomic situation from a livelihood perspective. These studies investigate the function of institutions and other types of assets in sustaining life.

Results and Discussions

The main steps in technical research are data analysis and interpretation. Data analysis leads to inferences, which are necessary for any study to be useful. Generalizations and conclusions are derived in the social sciences based on the features and attitudes of the respondents. This section was presented the outcomes of study which has been deliberated, examined and understood to provide appropriate recommendations.

Gender

Distribution of the respondents according to their gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	82	68.3
Female	38	31.7

Total	120	100.0
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This table presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents based on their gender. The data categorizes respondents into two groups Male and Female. Out of the 120 respondents surveyed, 82 respondents, comprising 68.3% of the

total, identify as Male. This indicates that a significant majority of the surveyed population are male individuals. The Female category consists of 38 respondents, accounting for 31.7% of the total.

Age

Distribution of the respondents according to their age

Age (Years)	Frequency	Percentage
1- 25 years	17	14.2
< 25 - 45 years	38	31.7
< 45 - 60	47	39.2
Above 60	18	15.0
Total	120	100.0

The above table indicates that the distribution of patients across different age groups in a sample of 120 individuals. The age groups are categorized as follows: 1-25 years, < 25 - 45 years, < 45 - 60 years, and above 60 years. The largest proportion of patients falls into the age group of 45 to 60 years, accounting for 39.2%

of the total sample. This is followed by the age group of 25 to 45 years, making up 31.7% of the sample. The younger age group of 1 to 25 years comprises 14.2% of the patients, while the older age group above 60 years accounts for 15.0%.

Residence status

Distribution of the respondents according to their residence status

Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	81	67.5
Urban	39	32.5
Total	120	100.0

The above table showed that the distribution of patients based on their residence in a sample of 120 individuals. The patients are divided into two categories: rural and urban. The majority of patients,

constituting 67.5% of the total sample, reside in rural areas. On the other hand, 32.5% of the patients are from urban areas.

Type of tenure ship

Distribution of the respondents according to their type of Tenure ship

Types of tenure ship	Frequency	Percentage
Owner	23	19.2
Tenant	48	40.0
Owner-cum-tenant	49	40.8
Total	120	100.0

The above table shows that the respondents are categorized into three group's owners, tenants, and

owner-cum-tenants. Among the respondent's population, 40.8% are classified as owner-cum-

tenants, indicating a relatively significant proportion of individuals who both own and rent the property they inhabit. The second largest group comprises tenants, constituting 40.0% of the sample,

suggesting a considerable number of individuals who reside in properties owned by others. Owners make up 19.2% of the patients, representing individuals who fully own the property they live in.

Ranking of the respondents’ perceptions about economic opportunities impact of community assets on the livelihoods of rural people

Economic opportunities	Weighted Score	Mean	S. D	Ranked order
Unemployment rates and job prospects	414	3.06	1.056	1
Income levels and sources of income for community members	335	3.07	1.14	2
Poverty levels and income inequality measures	335	3.22	1.030	3
Economic sectors dominant in the community (agriculture, industry, services)	247	3.33	.945	4
Employment opportunities within the community	240	2.00	0.79	5

The above table indicates that the various economic opportunities and their corresponding mean scores, standard deviations, variances, and ranked orders, along with weighted scores for a community. The economic opportunities evaluated include Unemployment rates and job prospects. Income levels and sources of income for community members. Poverty levels and income inequality measures, Economic sectors dominant in the community (agriculture, industry, services), and Employment opportunities within the community. Based on the mean scores, the community perceives Employment opportunities within the community to be the least favorable economic opportunity, with a mean score of 2.00. This indicates that community members feel that the availability of jobs within their locality is relatively limited or unsatisfactory. The opportunity related to Economic sectors dominant in the community (agriculture, industry, services) received a mean score of 3.33, suggesting that the community perceives a relatively higher degree of economic activity and diversity in the dominant sectors. The opportunities related to Unemployment rates and job prospects and Income levels and sources of income for

community members share similar mean scores of 3.06 and 3.07, respectively. This indicates that community members perceive similar levels of concern and satisfaction with regard to job prospects and income sources within the community. The opportunity related to Poverty levels and income inequality measures received a mean score of 3.22, suggesting that the community is moderately concerned about poverty levels and income disparities within its population. Furthermore, examining the weighted scores, Unemployment rates and job prospects ranks first with a weighted score of 414, indicating its high significance in the community's economic concerns. Income levels and sources of income for community members and Poverty levels and income inequality measures share the second rank, both with a weighted score of 335. The opportunity related to the Economic sectors dominant in the community ranks fourth with a weighted score of 247, and Employment opportunities within the community ranks fifth with a weighted score of 240. The frequency and percentage distributions of the responses are given in Appendix-I (Table:1).

Ranking of the respondents’ perceptions about Education and Skill Development that impact of community assets on livelihoods of rural people

Education and Skill Development	Weighted Score	Mean	S. D	Ranked order
Relevance of education and skills to local job market demands	427	3.38	.810	1
Education levels of community members	417	3.04	1.064	2
Education levels of community members	405	3.39	.892	3
Skill development initiatives and their effectiveness	396	3.56	.828	4
Access to quality education and vocational training programs	365	3.30	.931	5

The above table shows that the various aspects of education and skill development in a community, using mean scores, standard deviations (S.D.) weighted scores and ranked orders. These aspects include Relevance of education and skills to local job market demands, Education levels of community members, Skill development initiatives and their effectiveness, and Access to quality education and vocational training programs. According to the mean scores, the community rates Skill development initiatives and their effectiveness the highest, with a mean score of 3.56, indicating that residents perceive skill development initiatives to be relatively effective in enhancing their skills and employability. Relevance of education and skills to local job market demands received a mean score of 3.38, suggesting that the community perceives education and skills to be reasonably aligned with the demands of the local job market. The opportunity related to Education levels of community members has a mean score of 3.39, indicating that residents view the overall education levels of community members positively. Higher

standard deviations indicate greater variability in responses. Education levels of community members have the highest standard deviation and variance, implying a wider range of views regarding the education levels of individuals in the community. The ranked order reveals the relative importance of each aspect in the community. Relevance of education and skills to local job market demands ranks first with a weighted score of 427, indicating its high significance in the community's evaluation of education and skill development. Education levels of community members and Skill development initiatives and their effectiveness share the second rank, both with weighted scores of 417 and 396, respectively. The opportunity related to "Access to quality education and vocational training programs" ranks last with a weighted score of 365, suggesting that the community perceives access to such programs as less critical compared to other aspects. The frequency and percentage distributions of the responses are given in Appendix-I (Table:2).

Ranking of the respondents’ perceptions about healthcare and well-being that impact of community assets on livelihoods of rural people

Healthcare and Well-being	Weighted Score	Mean	S.D	Ranked order
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Access to healthcare insurance or social protection programs	408	3.30	.866	1
Availability and quality of healthcare services	407	3.14	.770	2
Sanitation and access to clean water	396	3.13	.949	3
Health indicators (e.g., life expectancy, disease prevalence)	377	3.40	.974	4
Presence of social networks and support systems	375	3.09	.850	5

The above table indicates that the various aspects of healthcare and well-being in a community, using mean scores, standard deviations (S.D.) weighted scores and ranked orders, these aspects include access to healthcare insurance or social protection programs, availability and quality of healthcare services, Sanitation and access to clean water, Health indicators (e.g., life expectancy, disease prevalence) and Presence of social networks and support systems. According to the mean scores, the community rates Health indicators (e.g., life expectancy, disease prevalence) the highest, with a mean score of 3.40, indicating that residents perceive the overall health indicators in the community positively. Access to healthcare insurance or social protection programs received a mean score of 3.30, suggesting that the community considers access to healthcare insurance or social protection programs as relatively satisfactory. The opportunities related to availability and quality of healthcare services and sanitation and access to clean water have mean scores of 3.14 and 3.13, respectively, indicating that residents view the availability and

quality of healthcare services and access to clean water with a positive outlook. The standard deviations and variances provide insight into the diversity of opinions or perceptions regarding each aspect. Health indicators have the highest standard deviation implying a wider range of views regarding the health status and disease prevalence within the community. The ranked order reveals the relative importance of each aspect in the community. Access to healthcare insurance or social protection programs ranks first with a weighted score of 408, indicating its high significance in the community's evaluation of healthcare and well-being. Availability and quality of healthcare services" ranks second with a weighted score of 407, closely followed by Sanitation and access to clean water with a weighted score of 396. Health indicators rank fourth with a weighted score of 377 while Presence of social networks and support systems ranks fifth with a weighted score of 375. The frequency and percentage distributions of the responses are given in Appendix-I (Table: 3).

Ranking of the respondents' perceptions about Social Capital and Community Networks that impact of community assets on livelihoods of rural people

Social Capital and Community Networks	Weighted Score	Mean	S. D	Ranked order
Access to information and resources through social connections	413	3.50	.898	1

Engagement in collective action or community initiatives	392	3.44	.986	2
Community cohesion and trust levels	371	3.27	.847	3

The above table indicates that the various aspects of social capital and community networks in a community, using mean scores, standard deviations (S.D.) weighted scores and ranked orders. According to the mean scores, the community rates access to information and resources through social connections the highest with a mean score of 3.50, indicating that residents perceive their ability to access information and resources through social connections as relatively positive. Engagement in collective action or community initiatives received a mean score of 3.44, suggesting that the community is actively engaged in collective actions and community initiatives. The opportunity related to Community cohesion and trust levels has a mean score of 3.27, indicating that residents view the level of community cohesion and trust positively. The standard deviations and variances

provide insight into the diversity of opinions or perceptions regarding each aspect. Higher standard deviations indicate greater variability in responses. The ranked order reveals the relative importance of each aspect in the community. Access to information and resources through social connections ranks first with a weighted score of 413, indicating its high significance in the community's evaluation of social capital and community networks. Engagement in collective action or community initiatives ranks second with a weighted score of 392, followed by Community cohesion and trust levels with a weighted score of 371. The frequency and percentage distributions of the responses are given in Appendix -I (Table:4)

Ranking of the respondents' perceptions about Entrepreneurship and Business Environment that impact of community assets on livelihoods of rural people

Entrepreneurship and Business Environment	Weighted Score	Mean	S.D	Ranked order
Presence of local businesses and entrepreneurship opportunities	414	3.18	.958	1
Regulatory environment and ease of doing business	406	3.23	.921	2
Support mechanisms for small and medium-sized enterprises	381	3.38	.963	3

The above table showed that the various aspects related to entrepreneurship and the business environment in a community, using mean scores, standard deviations (S.D.), weighted scores ranked orders. These aspects include presence of local businesses and entrepreneurship opportunities, regulatory environment and ease of doing business and support mechanisms for small and medium-sized enterprises. According to the mean scores, the

community rates Support mechanisms for small and medium-sized enterprises the highest, with a mean score of 3.38, indicating those residents perceive the availability of support mechanisms for small and medium-sized businesses positively. The regulatory environment and ease of doing business received a mean score of 3.23 suggesting that the community views the ease of doing business and regulatory environment with a positive outlook. Similarly, the

opportunity related to the presence of local businesses and entrepreneurship opportunities has a mean score of 3.18, indicating that residents see the presence of local businesses and entrepreneurship opportunities in a favorable light. The standard deviations and variances provide insight into the diversity of opinions or perceptions regarding each aspect. Higher standard deviations and variances indicate greater variability in responses. Presence of local businesses and entrepreneurship opportunities has the highest standard deviation and variance, implying a wider range of views regarding the presence of local businesses and opportunities for entrepreneurship

within the community. The ranked order reveals the relative importance of each aspect in the community. Presence of local businesses and entrepreneurship opportunities ranks first with a weighted score of 414 indicating its high significance in the community's evaluation of entrepreneurship and the business environment. Regulatory environment and ease of doing business ranks second with a weighted score of 406, followed by Support mechanisms for small and medium-sized enterprises with a weighted score of 381. The frequency and percentage distributions of the responses are given in Appendix-I (Table:5)

Ranking of the respondents’ perceptions about Hindering factors that impact of community assets on livelihoods of rural people

<i>Hindering factors</i>	Weighted Score	Mean	S. D	Ranked order
Weak coordination and collaboration among stakeholders	423	3.42	.765	1
Weak Governance and Institutional Capacity:	417	3.53	.978	2
Limited Access to Education and Skill Development:	414	3.23	1.075	3
Climatic variations	412	3.43	.905	4
Poor transportation networks and limited access to markets	411	3.38	.979	5
Lack of transparency, accountability, and effective decision-making processes	410	3.31	.741	6
Socio-cultural Challenges:	409	3.41	.783	7
Inadequate provision of basic amenities such as electricity, water, and sanitation	407	3.48	.820	8
Climate change impacts affecting the viability of certain assets (e.g., agriculture, water resources)	407	3.39	.901	9
High levels of poverty and limited income-generating opportunities	406	3.43	1.157	10
Lack of proper communication and connectivity infrastructure	405	3.28	1.115	11
Insufficient focus on relevant skills for local job market demands	404	3.32	.924	12
Lack of participation and engagement of community members in decision-making processes	401	3.34	.930	13
Resistance to new ideas or innovations due to cultural barriers	400	3.33	.863	14

Vulnerability to natural disasters or environmental degradation	399	3.33	.918	15
Inadequate educational institutions or poor quality of education	397	3.37	.934	16
Inadequate Infrastructure:	396	3.39	.802	17
Political instability or conflict that hinders progress and investment	393	3.28	.756	18
Limited capacity and resources of local governing bodies or community organizations	393	3.42	.967	19
Political and Policy Context:	392	3.27	1.068	20
Lack of supportive policies or regulations for community asset development	389	3.24	.733	21
Limited availability of vocational training programs and skill development initiatives	388	3.23	1.075	22
Limited Financial Resources	387	3.14	.938	23
Discrimination and marginalization of certain groups within the community	386	3.22	1.063	24
Limited access to natural resources for sustainable community asset development	385	3.21	.869	25
Low levels of community empowerment and self-efficacy	384	3.20	.913	26
Insufficient funding or investment for community development projects	377	3.38	.900	27
Deep-rooted social norms and traditions that hinder progress and change	370	3.08	.984	28
Lack of Awareness and Empowerment:	369	3.08	1.055	29
Limited awareness about the potential benefits of community asset development	351	2.93	.980	30
Inconsistent or changing government priorities and lack of long-term planning	334	3.20	.992	31
Lack of access to capital or loans for community initiatives	247	3.30	1.050	32

The above table indicates that the various economic opportunities and challenges in a community using mean scores, standard deviations (S.D.) weighted scores and ranked orders. These aspects encompass a wide range of factors that influence economic development and community well-being. The data highlights the perceptions of the community members regarding these factors. The ranked order reveals that the community considers Weak Governance and Institutional Capacity as the most critical challenge ranked 23rd with a weighted score of 417. Access to Education and Skill Development ranked 24th with a weighted score of 414. The community recognizes the importance of education and skill development

opportunities to improve economic prospects and overall well-being. Climatic variations and Poor transportation networks and limited access to markets are ranked 25th and 26th, respectively, indicating concerns related to environmental factors and connectivity challenges that may hinder economic activities and access to markets. The data reveals that the community faces challenges such as High levels of poverty and limited income-generating opportunities Inadequate provision of basic amenities and Climate change impacts affecting the viability of certain assets. These factors are ranked 31st, 29th, and 30th, respectively, suggesting that poverty, inadequate infrastructure, and climate change impacts are

significant concerns affecting economic opportunities and overall community development. Other challenges include Lack of proper communication and connectivity infrastructure Insufficient focus on relevant skills for local job market demands, Lack of participation and engagement of community members in decision-making processes and resistance to new ideas or innovations due to cultural barriers. These factors are ranked between 32nd and 35th, highlighting various social and cultural barriers that may impede progress and innovation within the community. The data emphasizes the importance of community awareness and empowerment in addressing economic challenges. Limited awareness about the potential benefits of community asset development and Lack of Awareness and Empowerment are ranked 51st and 50th, respectively, underscoring the need for community engagement and education to foster a collective understanding of the benefits and opportunities of community asset development. The frequency and percentage distributions of the responses are given in Appendix-I (Table:6)

Major findings

- The main findings in the table indicate that in the studied population (n=120), 67.5% of individuals resided in rural areas, while 32.5% lived in urban areas.
- The majority finding in the size of land holdings among the studied population (n=120) is that 40.0% of individuals had both Medium (above 12.5-25 acres) and Large (>25 acres) land holdings, each category representing equal proportions. 19.2% had Small (<12.5 acres) land holdings, and only 0.8% reported Zero land holdings.
- The main findings indicate that among the studied population (n=120), 40.8% of individuals had an Owner-cum-tenant tenure ship, followed by 40.0% as Tenants. Owners constituted 19.2% of the participants.
- The primary observations indicate that among the 120 participants in the study, 60.8% had a total area under their own cultivation categorized as Small (<12.5 acres), while 20.8% had a Large (>25 acres) area, and 18.3% reported a Medium (above 12.5-25 acres) area under their cultivation.
- According to the results highest proportion of individuals, 38.3%, falls within the 41000-50000 income range among the studied population (n=120).
- The primary observations indicate that the income sources of the 120 participants. The majority, accounting for 70.0%, earned their income from Agriculture, while 17.5% obtained it from Government sources, and 12.5% from Primary sources.
- The main findings demonstrate the distribution of family types among the studied population (n=120). The majority, 67.5%, belonged to nuclear families, while 32.5% were part of Joint families.
- According to the results a total number of family members among the studied population (n=120). The highest proportion, 38.3%, had 6-7 family members, followed by 23.3% with above 7 members, 22.5% with 3-4 members, and 15.8% with 5-6 members.
- The majority finding shows that the highest extent of income from sources reported by the studied population (n=120) is a "Very Low" extent, accounting for 31.7% of the respondents.
- A large majority of respondents unemployment rates and job prospects received the highest importance among the economic opportunities, with a weighted score of 414 and a mean of 3.06.
- The majority findings indicate that the area of Healthcare and Well-being is Access to healthcare insurance or social protection programs with a weighted score of 408 and a mean of 3.30.
- The majority findings indicate that the domain of Social Capital and Community Networks is "Access to information and resources through social connections" with a weighted score of 413 and a mean of 3.50, indicating its highest importance among the studied population.
- The main finding in the domain of Entrepreneurship and Business Environment is the high importance of "Presence of local

businesses and entrepreneurship opportunities" with a weighted score of 414 and a mean of 3.18.

- The majority finding in the hindering factors for community asset development is the top-ranked factor "Weak coordination and collaboration among stakeholders" with a weighted score of 423 and a mean of 3.42, highlighting the critical role of effective coordination in overcoming challenges.

Conclusion

The respondents in the study highlighted several urgent needs within the communities that could be addressed through the development of community assets. These needs include poverty reduction, improved access to healthcare, enhanced education opportunities, economic development, affordable housing, safe public spaces, and job training and employment opportunities. The research findings indicated that the development of community assets can significantly enhance livelihood opportunities for community members in various ways. The establishment of community assets such as parks, community centers, and public spaces can generate new employment opportunities within the community. The development of community assets like transportation infrastructure and amenities can attract businesses to the area, leading to the creation of additional job opportunities. Community assets such as schools and vocational training centers can provide community members with better access to education and training, enabling them to acquire new skills and enhance their employability. Community assets like public markets and commercial spaces can offer local businesses new avenues to promote and sell their products and services, thus boosting economic growth within the community. It was evident from the study that the development of community assets has the potential to significantly improve livelihood opportunities for community members, especially those engaged in farming as their primary source of income in rural areas. The analysis revealed that approximately 70% of rural residents derived their livelihood from farming, while 17.5% were government employees, and 12.5% held private jobs. In conclusion, establishing effective partnerships with local

businesses, government agencies, and community organizations is crucial to ensure the proper maintenance and management of community assets. By allocating necessary resources and support, we can foster the creation of thriving and sustainable communities that cater to the needs of all residents.

Recommendations & Suggestions

Here are some general suggestions for developing community assets:

Assess community needs: Conduct a comprehensive assessment to determine the specific needs and priorities of the community. This can be achieved by actively involving community members, local organizations, and other relevant stakeholders.

Develop a strategic plan: Create a well-defined plan that outlines the steps required to address the identified needs. This plan should include strategies for securing funding, establishing partnerships with local organizations, and engaging key stakeholders.

Foster collaborations: Cultivate partnerships and collaborations with local organizations, businesses, and stakeholders who can contribute resources and support to the community development initiatives. This collaborative approach enhances the effectiveness and sustainability of the projects.

Emphasize sustainability: Ensure the long-term sustainability of community assets by developing a comprehensive plan that addresses maintenance, funding sources, and community engagement. This approach helps to maintain the assets and ensures their ongoing benefits for the community.

Encourage community participation: Engage the community actively throughout the development process to ensure that their voices are heard and that the assets align with their needs. This can be accomplished through community meetings, surveys, focus groups, and involving community members in decision-making.

Celebrate achievements: Recognize and celebrate the positive impact of community assets on the livelihoods of the farming community. This can be done through community events, success stories, testimonials, and engagement with local media to raise awareness and support for the projects.

Diversify community assets: Consider developing a range of community assets that cater to different needs. For example, establish public parks for

recreational activities, establish health clinics to provide essential healthcare services, promote education programs to enhance skills and knowledge, and support economic development and entrepreneurship opportunities within the community.

By implementing these recommendations, it is expected that the community assets in Tehsil Faisalabad can be enhanced, leading to improved livelihoods and overall well-being of the farming community.

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